

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FACTORS DETERMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FINANCIAL SECURITY AT THE MICRO AND MACRO LEVELS

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Abstract

A financial and economic security system is one of the most important conditions for the effective functioning and development of both business and government activity in the country. The financial and economic security of economic entities and the state is a complex system, encompassing a set of internal and external indicators aimed at the efficient use of resources. Currently, the management of financial resources and the optimization of their use, as well as the use of financial instruments aimed at ensuring stable and efficient financial and economic processes, are becoming increasingly important. This article examines financial security at the micro and macro levels. It identifies factors influencing financial security that must be considered in the financial and economic activities of economic entities and the implementation of state financial policy.

Keywords: security, financial security, entrepreneurship, business entities, public policy.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the world has seen a sharpening of contradictions in various spheres of human activity, manifested in the aggravation of economic phenomena, the intensification of shadow processes, and increased international competition, including unfair competition.

The impact of these phenomena and processes on the domestic economy is exacerbated by financial instability and the military-political situation, the imposition of sanctions, and a number of other factors.

Under these conditions, businesses are experiencing loss of markets, deteriorating solvency, declining financial stability, bankruptcies, and corporate raiding. The unresolved challenges in this area and the combination of all the aforementioned negative consequences prevent the achievement of the required level of economic growth, hinder effective economic restructuring, and negatively impact our country's financial policy and budgetary process.

All of this necessitates special attention to the development of an effective financial security system for domestic businesses, which should be based on a combination of advances in modern economic science, innovative approaches to entrepreneurial activity, as well as financial diagnostics and crisis management tools.

The current state of finance at the micro and macro levels is largely dependent on the influence of global financial and economic processes. Over the past five years, global financial and economic processes have shown no overall positive trend. This trend is due to financial instability and the uncertainty of development prospects.

Financial instability in the global economy significantly impacts the financial security of businesses (micro level) and the state (macro level), thereby hindering the development of the domestic economy and contributing to the growth of social tensions in the country.

Many domestic and international scholars have devoted attention to issues of financial security at the macro and microeconomic levels.

However, despite numerous studies exploring these issues, a number of issues related to financial security at the micro and macro levels remain unresolved. This trend is driven by periodic changes in the internal and external environment, changes in the financial and economic situation at both the national and individual business levels, and significant financial and economic shifts in the global economy.

The main challenge in researching financial security issues at the micro and macro levels is identifying the factors influencing and interrelations between individual levels of financial security.

2. Discussion

The financial security of business entities and the financial security of the state represent different levels of financial security within a socio-economic system. Each of these levels has its own essential and substantive characteristics, influencing factors, and final results.

According to I.A. Blank, the financial security of business entities is endowed with key characteristics, including:

- "...the volume and structure of financial resources;
- sources of financial resources and their cost;
- the volume and structure of the enterprise's total capital;
- directions, volumes, and structure of financial resource use;
- the ratio of enterprise revenues to expenses;
- the ratio of internal and external sources of financial resource generation;
- the chosen strategy and operational-tactical model for financial support of activities;
- the level of financial risk and profit generation volumes;
- profit quality and its sufficiency for self-financing;
- the share and quality of borrowed funds in the enterprise's financial resources;
- the level of solvency, liquidity, financial stability, and financial solvency of the enterprise;

- the availability of reserves and the enterprise's ability to quickly mobilize financial resources;
- flexibility of the enterprise's financial forecasting and planning system;
- the ability of the enterprise's financial system to rapidly adapt to the internal and external environment;
- the ownership structure of the enterprise's capital; enterprise value" [2].

All of this predetermines special attention to the development of an effective financial security system for domestic business entities, which should be based on a combination of the achievements of modern economic science, innovative approaches to entrepreneurial activity, as well as financial diagnostics and crisis management tools.

Considering the development of financial and economic processes at the level of economic entities, an analysis of literary sources on the identified issues allowed us to identify the following functions of the financial security system for business entities:

1. Preventive function, which is associated with the use of a set of measures aimed at preventing or reducing financial losses and with the ability to carry out preventive measures aimed at preventing and controlling the occurrence of potential threats to the financial condition of business entities.

2. The stabilization function, which involves creating and maintaining a business entity's financial balance, such that normal fluctuations in financial flows within the entity do not disrupt the patterns of its functioning and development. This function is closely linked to countering internal threats and risks.

3. The adaptive function, which involves creating a system of flexible and rapid response to minor changes in the external economic environment, preventing disruption to the business entity's equilibrium development. This function will increase the entity's resilience to non-systemic external threats and risks.

4. The protective function, which involves creating significant financial countermeasures to systemic threats and risks that could lead to a crisis even if the business entity is in a state of stable financial equilibrium.

5. The control function, which involves monitoring income, expenses, financial documentation, and ensuring compliance with applicable regulations during financial transactions.

Based on the above, "...the financial security of a business entity is a general characteristic of the financial status of the relevant business entity on a specified date, which indicates the financial capabilities and ability to fulfill obligations and function effectively in conditions of instability, uncertainty, and various financial and business risks" [5].

The financial security of business entities is determined by the following:

Firstly, the financial security of business entities is one of the important characteristics of their financial system. If the level of financial security is high, then it can be argued that the financial system of the business entity meets modern requirements and development conditions. If the level of financial security is low or unsatisfactory, this means that the financial system is

unstable, does not meet modern development needs, etc.

Secondly, the financial security of business entities is one of the basic components for building a state financial system. That is, if the financial system at the level of the business entity is balanced, its. This can be considered effective, positively influencing the state's financial system as a whole. Otherwise, this sequence negatively impacts the state's financial security.

Thirdly, the financial security of business entities significantly influences the financial security of households, due to the flow of funds between business entities and households. The financial stability and solvency of enterprises is the key to the financial security of households, which will receive significant sums of funds from business entities. Moreover, the growth of payments from business entities to households directly depends on the level of financial security of the former.

Also, according to M.M. Orucov, "...the financial security of the state is considered as a dynamic state of security, competitiveness, stability, and sustainable development of the financial system, based on the financial solvency of enterprises, which ensures the accepted conditions and necessary resources for expanded reproduction and economic growth [8]."

The financial security of the state is determined by the financial capabilities of business entities and their levels of financial security. At the same time, the financial security of the state significantly impacts the financial security of business entities. Consequently, the financial security of business entities and the state are interrelated concepts, the level of influence of which is determined by many factors, conditions, and components.

First, the financial security of the state is a more complex and multifaceted concept, dependent on a significantly greater number of factors, conditions, and components than the financial security of business entities.

Second, the financial security of the state is determined by the state's financial strategy and tactics, as well as its financial, budgetary, tax, foreign exchange, monetary, customs, and investment policies. If the state has significant financial resources and a small budget deficit, this guarantees financial stability and financial security.

Third, the financial security of the state depends on the structure of the economy, the effective distribution of incoming and outgoing cash flows, the presence of a positive foreign trade balance, stable and dynamic economic development, and significant GDP growth. In this case, if the internal structure of the domestic economy is sufficiently balanced—that is, if various sectors (industry, agriculture, transportation, etc.) are developed, and the country's economy is equally oriented toward both foreign and domestic markets—then the level of the state's financial security will be significantly higher than if the country's economy is oriented toward either exports, imports, or commodity markets.

Fourth, the state's financial security largely depends on global financial and economic processes and trends. This trend is driven by the significant scale of globalization and economic integration, as well as the

interconnectedness of various markets, particularly financial ones. The financial problems of one large country, such as the United States or a group of countries, particularly the EU, undoubtedly impact the financial situation of all other countries due to changes in the supply and demand for goods and services, price fluctuations, etc.

Fifth, the state's financial security depends on the domestic situation in the country, the stability of the political system, the level of development of democratic institutions, the level of regulatory framework for the economy, law enforcement, the level of corruption, and the desire of the population to develop and support their country.

It should be noted that the state's financial security depends not only on the financial solvency of enterprises in the real sector of the economy, but also on the financial solvency of business entities in the financial sector, particularly banking institutions. In recent years, banks, insurance companies, and financial investment companies have been responsible for a number of global-scale financial problems, significantly reducing the level of financial security not only of the state but also of other entities, particularly enterprises in the real sector and households.

As practice shows, the financial security of entrepreneurship is influenced by a significant range of internal and external factors.

Internal factors should primarily include factors that are not only taken into account but also manageable, that is, measures can be taken to reduce negative effects, neutralize threats, and compensate for losses due to the realization of risks. Effective management of internal factors also helps ensure the growth of basic financial indicators, which positively impact the financial system of a business entity, that is, the level of its financial security. External factors include those that are difficult to account for in current financial and economic activities, but can be taken into account when developing medium- and long-term financial and economic plans.

Research into the impact of internal factors on the level of financial security shows that they:

- a) can only be identified;
- b) can be identified and taken into account in financial and economic activities;
- c) can be identified, taken into account, and managed in the process of financial and economic activities.

In turn, external factors influencing the level of financial security of business entities should be divided into groups and subgroups.

1. Macro-level factors that:
 - a) cannot be identified before they occur;
 - b) can only be identified before they occur;
 - c) can be identified and partially taken into account in the process of financial and economic activities;
 - d) can be identified and fully taken into account in the process of financial and economic activities.
2. Meso-level factors that:
 - a) cannot be identified before they occur;
 - b) can only be identified before they occur;
 - c) can be identified and taken into account in the financial and economic process;

d) can be identified, taken into account, and partially neutralized.

3. Micro-level factors that:

- a) can be identified;
- b) can be identified and partially taken into account.

It is also advisable to systematize internal and external factors, which are divided into appropriate groups, according to their quantitative and qualitative characteristics.

For example, most internal factors affecting the level of financial security of business entities can be classified as quantitative, that is, they have a quantitative characteristic and can be accounted for using factor or regression-correlation analysis. At the same time, external factors, in most cases, have a qualitative characteristic, that is, they are not amenable to, or are not sufficiently amenable to, quantitative processing using factor or regression-correlation analysis.

The interaction between the financial security of the state and economic entities results in mutual positive and negative influences, which contribute to:

1) at the state level: growth in budget revenues and expenditures, an enhanced state credit rating, an improved investment climate, and increased financial capacity for the state's socio-economic system;

2) at the level of economic entities: satisfying the interests of owners, satisfying the interests of employees, meeting state financial requirements, and meeting creditors' financial requirements.

The interaction of financial security at the micro and macro levels allows for the alignment of the interests of individual economic entities and the resolution of a number of problems related to global economic processes. Improving the level of financial security of the state and economic entities has a positive impact on social processes at the micro and macro levels. Through the flow of financial resources between the state and economic entities, the interests of households are protected and the financial capacity of the population increases.

3. Conclusion

The conducted research allows us to formulate the following conclusions.

First, the financial security of business entities and the state should be considered as independent but inter-related concepts.

Second, the financial security of business entities and the state depends on internal and external factors.

However, the factors themselves influencing the financial security of business entities and the state differ due to objective and subjective circumstances.

Third, the relationship between the financial security of the state and business entities has both positive and negative effects, affecting the final performance of their financial systems.

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